

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE DIGITAL MODEL IN THE BUSINESS ECOSYSTEM OF MSMEs A STUDY IN LEBAK REGENCY

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Abstract

The government has implemented a policy to support the growth of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) through collaboration with minimarkets. This creates an opportunity for suppliers to sell their products through minimarkets network and generates competition for market access. To maximize the benefits for the local economy, the government should ensure that the presence of minimarkets is beneficial. Therefore, this study aimed to examine the collaborative governance model in the business ecosystem of food processing MSMEs and minimarkets, using Alfamart and Indomaret in Lebak Regency as a case study. A qualitative and descriptive approach was used, and data were collected through interviews, literature reviews, observations, and documentation. The findings showed a collaborative governance model in building the business ecosystem of food processing MSMEs and minimarkets, based on 8 dimensions. Collaborative governance has been running but is still constrained, so that in its implementation to realize business continuity it needs to be supported by business ecosystem dimensions so that we can find a new model of collaborative governance in the MSME business ecosystem. As for practically, the leading sector in this collaboration is the Regent as the head of the Region and the DPRD of Lebak Regency as the legislature.

Keywords: Collaborative Governance Model, Business Ecosystem, MSMEs, and Minimarkets.

1. INTRODUCTION

Retail markets play a significant role in countries such as Southern and Western Europe due to increasing population density and growing needs [1]. It is located near the city center to cater to the high population density in Paris. In China, modern retail serves as a marketing agent for vegetable farmers [2]. In Indonesia, the development of minimarkets has positively impacted the economy, such as rising land prices, growth of local businesses, and job creation. Meanwhile, minimarkets such as Indomaret and Alfamart provide quality goods and build trust with the community, fulfilling their needs. These minimarkets also offer opportunities for partnerships with MSMEs actors, including marketing their products through repackaging with a brand of choice or selling them on store shelves [3].

The empirical condition shows the interdependence of various actors, hence, it is appropriate to use the collaborative governance concept. In a different context, ecosystems arise when all elements cannot survive without each other and become an inseparable unity [4,5]. The oppression of one creature can cause the loss of another, and this concept is considered appropriate for studying the examined issue. Furthermore, the existence of minimarkets should maintain a balance by providing benefits, such as establishing a partnership with other business actors. The ecosystem theory was created in 1935 as an ecological science studying the

interaction between biological systems and the environment, introduced by Arthur George Tansley [6]. Furthermore, this theory was adopted as an entrepreneurial ecosystem because it highly depends on the environment.

This study is conducted in Lebak Regency, which is geographically the largest area at 35.46% in Banten Province [7]. This regency has some natural potential, such as plantation products, agriculture, and tourism. Furthermore, it has the largest Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) in Banten Province.

The data indicated that Lebak Regency has the most MSMEs in Banten Province. It is dominated by the food and beverage sector, employing the most workers compared to others [8]. This regency is in second place among eight others in terms of the poverty rate in 2019-2021 [9]. This empirical condition showed that the presence of MSMEs has not fully significantly impacted a region's economy. Some of the problems in this research namely;

- (1) The weak relationships, communication, and commitment among actors with their respective authorities operate in a dependent manner.
- (2) The guidance and facilitation provided by the government are not integrated. Therefore, there is an imbalance of resources among actors, and some products partnered with MSMEs, such as coffee. However, this commitment cannot be fully implemented due to the unreliable availability of raw materials.
- (3) Lack of Understanding and information for MSMEs actors where some do not have a halal certificate and others have already expired.
- (4) The government provides no integrated complaint mechanism, and in handling minimarkets, the complexity of the problems faced by MSMEs actors requires intervention from various parties, one of which is involved in realizing the partnership. This contains complaints experienced by various parties who feel disadvantaged.
- (5) The absence of strict supervision and sanctions for minimarket managers who do not comply with regulations. Minimarket managers are not fully compliant with the regulations that require the provision of space, but in some Alfamart and Indomaret locations, there is no space for MSMEs products.

The novelty in this study based on empirical conditions shows that there is an imbalance between large companies, in this case minimarkets and small companies [10,11]. Based on these empirical conditions, a partnership is needed. In general, partnerships have been extensively studied in several fields, for example in cross-cultural [12], health and social [13], agriculture, and education [14] this includes teacher education partnerships and students, partnerships in library management [15], partnerships between companies and NGOs [16], while the benefits of partnerships are used as promotional media that become market access for MSME development [17,18], partnerships as the survival of SMEs [19], as well as supporting economic growth [20], reducing operating costs and providing customer satisfaction [21], as an effective interconnectivity strategy [22], solving social problems [23], mutual need and benefit. However, the partnership in Lebak Regency is very difficult to realize

in practice when the parties involved work alone, therefore researchers try to combine the concept of collaborative governance which was previously studied in different empirical studies [24] with ecosystem theory from ecology and biology emphasizing the existence of balance, then developed into economics and management into a business ecosystem to get a metatheoretical construction.

This study aims to examine the implementation of collaborative governance between MSMEs and minimarkets and formulate a model based on the intersection of the business ecosystem and collaborative governance theories in Lebak Regency.

2. THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.1 Collaborative Governance Model and Business Ecosystem

Collaborative governance is present as a new strategy in governance. As Ansell and Gash [25] revealed that collaborative governance is a governance arrangement that involves more than one public institution and non-government actors. In more detail, this collaborative governance model can be described as follows (Figure 1):

In general, the Ansell and Gash (2008) model has variables;

- Initial conditions, many failed collaboration processes due to differences in views between stakeholders and stakeholders.
- Institutional design. The first aspect of institutional design is participatory inclusiveness as Chirslip and Larson in Ansel and Gash [25] suggests that: "The first condition of successful collaboration is that it must be broadly inclusive of all stakeholders who are affected by or care about the issue.

- c) Facilitative leadership, this leadership can bring all parties to negotiate and negotiate to solve problems.
- d) Collaborative process. Collaborative process is a cycle. The collaboration process includes;
 - (1) Face to face dialogue,
 - (2) building trust (Trust building) collaborative processes are not only about negotiations but also about building trust between stakeholders [26],
 - (3) Commitment to the process,
 - (4) Shared understanding, is an agreement on the definition of the problem,
 - (5) Intermediate outcome. A number of case studies show that collaboration is more successful when the goals and concrete benefits of collaboration are visible and realized in the long term [27,28].

To complement this model, the business ecosystem also has actors who play a role including customers, markets and suppliers [29], and the structure in the entrepreneurial ecosystem includes 6 (six) pillars that form it, namely

- (i) Cultural conduciveness (tolerance of risk and failure, positive outlook on entrepreneurship);
- (ii) Supportive leadership and policymaking such as incentives, rules/regulations, policies and supportive leadership (regulatory incentives, support from public institutions);
- (iii) Adequate financing (microcredit, venture capital, etc.);
- (iv) Human capital / human resources (HR)/ (education and training institutions, HR skills);
- (v) Market availability and ability to absorb products;and
- (vi) Support from other institutions and infrastructure (law, legal, accounting, computerization and IT as well as entrepreneurial groups) [30].

2.2 Definition of Collaboration

The definition of collaboration, according to Lowe et al. (1988), is "working together" to utilize resources, such as information, finances, and human resources, among several stakeholders to provide answers to problems that cannot be solved by an individual [31]. This concept is further described as a dynamic and synergistic series of processes among multiple actors [32]. Meanwhile, this study focuses on collaboration between actors in the business ecosystem partnership between MSMEs and minimarkets, involving the government, private sector, and both MSMEs and minimarkets. It is based on mapping articles using nvivo tools, with the following being some of the theoretical dimensions used (Figure 2).

Networks and collaboration are terms that describe the interdependence of organizations in addressing a common problem, and this relationship is often referred to as governance. According to Frederickson [33], the term "public administration" is narrowly defined as government administration, focusing only on political, budget, personnel, and service provision issues. However, it should encompass a wider range of public concerns, including non-profit organizations, businesses, and all actors involved in interactions. The study of public administration encompassed not only the activities of government and non-government organizations but also the interactions between them that support each other.

2.3 Definition of Business Ecosystem

The concept of ecosystem originates from ecology, where it is defined as the interaction of living organisms with their physical environment. In this context, the entrepreneurial ecosystem can be seen as a discovery-based system, with two ontologies. The first view the ecosystem as a well-organized system regulated by nature, with a balance between organisms and other elements. The second, from a biological perspective, consider the cooperation of actors and external factors to understand the development and change of the ecosystem [34].

The term ecosystem was first introduced by Tansley [35] in the field of biology as an interactive system of living organisms in both biotic and abiotic environments. The business ecosystem as the interaction of capital, customers, and the ability to generate innovation, similar to species thriving due to the influence of natural resources such as sunlight, water, and soil nutrients. Furthermore, the study of the business ecosystem has evolved to encompass training, human resources skills, market absorption, and support from other institutions such as legal, accounting, computerization, IT, and entrepreneurship groups.

In the context of corporate networks that collaborate, Spigel [36] examined the need for interaction between one institution and another allowing mutual sharing of knowledge,

technology, and innovation. In the business ecosystem, there are three components, namely cultural, social, and material. In this context [36], culture can be seen from two sides, behavior, and history. Aoyama [37] explained that regional culture can influence entrepreneurial activities by forming practices and norms accepted by society. Meanwhile, social attributes in the entrepreneurial ecosystem are interpreted as resources from networks that exist within a society. Nijkamp [38] and Stuart and Sorenson [39] showed the importance of social networks and capital in the entrepreneurial process. In addition, social networks play a role as a channel for new knowledge that helps entrepreneurs in terms of entrepreneurial perspective and skills.

3. STUDY METHOD AND LOCATION

This qualitative study was conducted using a case study to obtain comprehensive information on collaborative governance in the partnership between MSMEs actors and minimarkets approach. Furthermore, it attempted to explore the case being studied in detail using written data sources. Data collection techniques using primary data and secondary data include; observation, interviews with several informants and documentation techniques. The validity of the data used used source triangulation, namely the researcher interviewed several informants and technical triangulation, namely several research techniques such as interviews, observation and document review. The data analysis used includes;

- (1) Data collection, namely collecting data both primary data and secondary data,
- (2) Data reduction, where the researcher conducts a data review,
- (3) Data display, after the data has been reviewed and reduced the next step is data presentation,
- (4) after the data is presented The next step is to carry out a simuplan based on data analysis.

The location involved was several sub-districts in the Lebak Regency area which have processing business centers as follows (Table 1):

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The franchise retail development has not yet directly impacted MSMEs actors who cannot market their processed products in these franchises, even in remote villages. This has prompted the Lebak Regency government to make promising breakthroughs for MSMEs development. Meanwhile, collaboration is necessary and determined by the starting condition in which all stakeholders are involved to build a business ecosystem between food processing MSMEs and minimarkets. This starting condition facilitates cooperation between institutions and stakeholders. The emergence of problems in managing requirements for entry into modern markets, as well as the pros and cons associated with the existence of minimarkets are the reasons for the need for multi-actor collaboration. This study found two collaboration governance models in the business ecosystem, namely:

4.1 Findings of an Empirical Collaborative Governance Model in the business ecosystem of food processing MSMEs and minimarkets

Based on empirical conditions, collaboration is carried out from upstream to downstream. From upstream, the actors involved are minimarkets, MSMEs actors, the One Stop Investment Service, the Health Department, the Legislative Regent, the MSMEs Community, and the Chamber of Commerce both in dialogue, sit together, and pay attention to inputs in the form of aspirations, licensing arrangements, constraints faced such as difficulty to penetrate the mini market. This upstream collaboration is conducted to understand the root of the problems; therefore, the solutions provided are based on thoughts and inputs for the common good. The process is conducted reciprocally, continuously, and sustainably, resulting in a balanced business ecosystem [40]. Downstream collaboration is the spearhead where decision-makers and policy-makers are the head of the region and the legislative body because the permit granting is based on the approval of the head. The head of the region and the legislative body play their roles as leaders and executors, with the legislative body controlling and working to create synergies in performing their duties.

4.2 Findings of Collaborative Governance Theoretical Model in the Business Ecosystem of Food Processing MSMEs and Minimarkets

Referring to the collaboration governance framework, the findings include the following:

- (1) The pros and cons of the minimarkets emergence are an opportunity for partnership seen in the launch of MSMEs, but establishing this process is not easy. MSMEs entering the modern market are partially handled, hence, the need for collaboration by multiple actors and stakeholders is necessary [41–47].
- (2) Facilitative Leadership starts from the central to the local government. Leaders initiate discussion forums, mediation, and control. They become figures in building consensus and connecting various parties as coordinators. Leaders should provide solutions to the community, as well as have the responsibility to plan and implement the vision and mission. The dimensions that play a role in realizing Collaborative governance in the ecosystem of MSMEs and minimarkets actors in Lebak Regency are, first, leaders can facilitate showed that collaboration will be realized when leaders play a facilitating role [48,49].
- (3) Institution Design indicates that
 - a) The impact of regulation provides legal protection,
 - b) The basis of formation is due to the growing modern stores and the need for minimarkets to partner with small businesses,
 - c) The goal of this policy is to create a conducive and mutually beneficial business climate [50–59].
- (4) Collaboration is conducted through various activities to convey ideas, proposals, and solutions offered by training, socialization, discussion forums, and informal communication using the theme of drinking coffee together. Meanwhile, collaboration can

materialize when dialogue and face-to-face communication are conducted between stakeholders [60];[61];[62];[63]. Communication media is performed face-to-face and appreciated through training. The initiation is carried out sectorally to show the low dynamics of interaction between actors or organizations, hence, problems cannot be solved together immediately. These explain the low level of interactive meetings among stakeholders. The intensity of interactive meetings among is still heavily influenced by the dominance of one actor, namely the government.

- (5) The large number of MSMEs actors who have not partnered shows that there is still low trust between stakeholders. Control is not carried out, contingency conditions cause distrust, and partnerships built do not last long, specifically during the pandemic [64–68].
- (6) MSMEs and Minimarkets have a commitment outlined in the cooperation agreement. The head of the regional commitment and the circular letter No. 973/102 – DPMPTSP/V/2018 regarding the use of small and medium enterprise products serve as the foundation for this commitment. Furthermore, Regional Regulation No. 3 of 2012 and Regent Regulation No. 9 of 2018 relating to the protection and empowerment of traditional markets and the arrangement of shopping centers and modern shops also play a role in the commitment. This study showed that the basis for implementing this commitment is the cooperation agreement, the Regent's circular letter, instructions and appeals, and regional regulations [69–79].
- (7) The Lebak Regency Government entered into a joint understanding with Sumber Alfaria Trijaya Company to develop business, the products of micro and small actors, and minimarkets based on the principle of equality, mutual assistance, benefit, and fair treatment. Moreover, the government also made a memorandum of Understanding with Indomarco Company. There is a MoU and various activities to provide Understanding to actors. The increase in MSMEs in Lebak Regency is inseparable from the role of the regional government in encouraging community economic growth and employment for local workers. Synthesis is a result of field findings that there is a unification of relevant Understanding, hence, collaborative actors can learn together to find strategies to succeed in a business climate conducive and mutually beneficial to actors. *First*, the need for legality to become the basis for shared Understanding includes MoU, Lebak Regency regional regulations, vision, and mission. *Second*, efforts to foster a shared understanding can be carried out through guidance and training, audiences and focus group discussions, application of regional regulations sanctions, and appeals from the Regent. *Third*, mutual Understanding is built based on goals such as creating a conducive business climate and establishing a partnership. Moreover, business actors can understand the implementation process to fulfill the conditions needed to establish cooperation with minimarkets[80–89].
- (8) The development of retail franchises that have penetrated remote villages has not provided a direct impact on MSMEs actors in marketing their processed products at minimarkets[90–97].

- (9) The culture shows that first; the business idea comes from an idea, not from generations. Second, the uniqueness created by MSMEs products is uniqueness in taste, variants of benefits, and net. Third, the equipment used is still very simple[98–103].
- (10) Understanding MSMEs actors requires both hard and soft skills. The key factors affecting knowledge in this area include
- 1) Community perception and potential opportunities due to available resources, cheap raw materials, utilization of natural resources, local labor, and market prospects.
 - 2) The benefits of knowing to include having a clear vision and mission, identifying opportunities and threats, and promoting market opportunities through collaboration.
 - 3) Information can be obtained through invitations, social media, and forums.
 - 4) Training is crucial for developing both soft and hard skills.
 - 5) Formal and informal education also play a role in developing knowledge.
 - 6) Hands-on experience through relationships and previous employment are valuable[104–109]
- (11) Regional conditions, both natural and social that characterize a region, are one of the special characteristics in increasing the rate of population growth and the potential for abundant resources but can cause injustice[110–122].

Specifically, the application of the collaborative governance model in the business ecosystem has an interrelated relationship seen in the following figure; According to the theory of Ansell and Gash (2008), in the dimension of institution design, the government's position as an initiator in regulating and making regulations that the need for a conducive business climate is mutually beneficial. This is based on the dominance of large companies spread in several regions, one of which is in Lebak Regency. The dominance needs a balance; therefore, this study tries to adopt the business ecosystem theory to create mutually beneficial harmony. Several factors become important points, first, the role of this leader is a public figure who can build consensus, communicate and interact by directing and promoting based on the goal of solving problems to achieve the vision and mission. Leaders in the regional apparatus organization are the head of the department based on competence and experience.

Second, collaboration arises because of problems that cannot be solved sectorally. Therefore, it is necessary to involve various parties from the government, the private sector, and the community in synergy. Collaboration is conducted with meetings formally, for example, through socialization, technical guidance, and training, as well as informal meeting in the form of community discussions and chats. Third, the goals to be achieved in synergizing the efforts of large companies and processed food MSMEs require attention to geographical studies that determine natural and social potential, the need for support to provide strengthening both morally and financially, policies favoring weak business actors, and technological support. Fourth, a collaboration that has been running needs commitment from various parties in the form of support for law enforcement or regulation, according to the agreement. Fifth, trust can

be built when mutually beneficial goals are achieved. Therefore, for MSMEs and minimarkets to partner and create conducive business conditions, it is necessary to strengthen food processing MSMEs actors in the ease of obtaining information, affordability, and distance in collecting facilities provided by the government. In addition, the limited skills possessed need to be strengthened and the private sector as a form of corporate social responsibility to jointly collaborate in increasing the innovation, and creativity of actors. For example, by providing free facilitation, training, and guidance, both carried out centrally and picking up the ball. It is expected that processed MSMEs actors in Lebak Regency can be competitive in marketing by utilizing the existence of minimarkets spread in various regions of Indonesia. Therefore, Lebak Regency raises the welfare of its people through business productivity involving various elements, such as the involvement of farmers in providing raw materials[123–126].

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The collaborative governance model in the business ecosystem of food processing MSMEs and minimarkets is theoretically seen from 8 dimensions, namely

- 1) Starting condition,
- 2) Facilitative Leadership,
- 3) Design Institute,
- 4) Face-to-face,
- 5) Trust Building,
- 6) Commitment,
- 7) Shared Understanding, and
- 8) Intermediate Outcome have been implemented but are still constrained.

In the implementation to realize business continuity, it needs to be supported by the dimensions of the ecosystem, including

- 1) Information,
- 2) Knowledge,
- 3) Market,
- 4) Culture,
- 5) Support, and
- 6) Geographic Areas.

Therefore, a new collaborative governance model can be found in the business ecosystem of food processing MSMEs and minimarkets. The leading sector in this collaboration is the Regent as the head of the region and the Lebak Regency Regional House of Representatives as

the legislative body.

Based on an analysis of field findings, a new model is proposed, namely the institutional design dimension, where the position of the government is the initiator in making regulations for a conducive business climate. This is based on the dominance of large companies, which are spreading in several regions, such as Lebak Regency. Meanwhile, the dominance requires balance to adopt the business ecosystem theory.

5.2 Recommendations

Referring to the results, there are several things that this study can theoretically suggest in the business ecosystem of food processing MSMEs and minimarkets, namely:

- (1) Perlunya sinergitas lembaga eksekutif dan lembaga legislative,
- (2) Diperlukannya kajian evaluasi penerapan peraturan daerah mengenai kemitraan UMKM dan minimarket,
- (3) Diperlukannya kajian redefinisi dan evaluasi untuk sinkronisasi visi misi,
- (4) Diperlukannya kajian optimalisasi keberadaan *Corporate Social Responsibility* (CSR).

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest of this work.

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